

Analysis of False Alarms in Control Charts

Análise de Alarmes Falsos em Gráficos de Controle
Análisis de Falsas Alarmas en Gráficos de Control

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Abstract:

Control charts are statistical tools used in Statistical Process Control (SPC) to monitor the stability of production processes. During monitoring, signals—referred to as alarms—may occur, indicating potential problems in the process. An inherent aspect of control charts is the occurrence of false alarms, which are indications of problems when no actual abnormality exists. This study aims to evaluate the frequency of false alarms based on different types of point patterns on the chart. The analysis was conducted through simulation using the Python programming language, and the results indicate that the frequency of false alarms increases with the inclusion of additional alarm types. The average number of inspections until a false alarm tends to decrease, dropping by up to 80% when five types of alarms are used.

Keywords: Statistical Process Control; Control Charts; False Alarms.

Resumo:

Os gráficos de controle são ferramentas estatísticas utilizadas no Controle Estatístico de Processo (CEP) para monitorar a estabilidade de processos produtivos. Durante o monitoramento podem ocorrer sinais descritos como alarmes que indicam problemas no processo e um aspecto invariável dos gráficos de controle é a ocorrência de alarmes falsos. Estes são indicações de problemas no processo quando não há anormalidade. O presente trabalho tem como objetivo avaliar a frequência de ocorrência de alarmes falsos de acordo com os tipos de padrões de pontos no gráfico. O estudo foi conduzido através de simulação utilizando a linguagem de programação Python e os resultados indicam que a frequência de alarmes falsos aumenta de acordo com o uso adicional de alarmes complementares e do seu tipo. O número médio de inspeções até o alarme falso tende a diminuir e cair até a 80% quando cinco tipos de alarmes forem utilizados.

Palavras-chave: Controle Estatístico de Processo; Carta de Controle; Alarme Falso.

Resumen:

Los gráficos de control son herramientas estadísticas utilizadas en el Control Estadístico de Procesos (SPC) para monitorear la estabilidad de los procesos de producción. Durante el monitoreo, puede haber signos descritos como alarmas que indiquen problemas en el proceso, y un aspecto invariable de los gráficos de control es la aparición de falsas alarmas. Estos son indicios de problemas en el proceso cuando no hay anomalías. El presente trabajo tiene como objetivo evaluar la frecuencia de ocurrencia de falsas alarmas de acuerdo con los tipos de patrones de puntos en el gráfico. El estudio se realizó mediante simulación utilizando el lenguaje de programación Python y los resultados indican que la frecuencia de falsas alarmas aumenta con el uso adicional de alarmas complementarias y su tipo. El número promedio de inspecciones hasta la falsa alarma tiende a disminuir y caer al 80% cuando se utilizan cinco tipos de alarmas.

Palabras clave: Control estadístico de procesos; Gráfico de control; Falsa alarma.

1. INTRODUCTION

Quality is a decisive factor for the success and survival of organizations that are constantly developing methods to deliver high-value-added products and services, satisfy customer demands, and reduce costs associated with poor quality. In this context, quality control becomes necessary as a formal tool and method to guarantee excellence.

Statistical Process Control (SPC) comprises a set of tools for evaluating, maintaining, and improving the quality of production processes. Among the various tools that make up SPC are control charts, also known as Shewhart charts. This technique uses statistical and graphical methods that allow those involved to act objectively and effectively when an abnormality occurs in the production process.

This paper analyzes the average control chart and the indication of a problem in the process when it is operating properly. The literature describes it as a false alarm (MONTGOMERY, 2009). In a production process, alarms can interrupt production for evaluation, and since the process is operating properly, the interruption was unnecessary.

In the design of control charts, it is necessary to specify their sensitivity to process deviations and avoid numerous false deviation indications. This study uses Monte Carlo simulation to evaluate the average number of false alarms for different types of abnormality patterns used in the control chart. The product of this work can be used to construct control charts.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Walter A. Shewhart is known as the creator of Statistical Process Control, a concept he developed while working at Bell Telephone in the 1920s. Laboratories (Reyes and Vicino, 2018). SPC provides tools for process quality control, including the control chart, a graph of a quality characteristic used to monitor the production process. Shewhart created this tool based on statistical methods that guarantee its operability.

There are several types of control charts, and their use depends on the quality characteristic being monitored and its associated probability distribution. A variable can be discrete when it assumes point values (usually whole numbers); examples include the number of defects per part and the number of defective parts in a batch. The probability distribution models are Binomial and the Poisson (Montgomery, 2009).

Another type of variable is the continuous variable, in which case the results are usually in the domain of real numbers, such as the diameter and weight of automotive parts. Among the various distribution models of continuous variables, the normal distribution stands out.

In the case of continuous variables, the most common control charts are the mean chart (\bar{x} chart), which seeks to analyze and monitor the population mean (μ) using the sample means (\bar{x}). Another widely used chart is the range chart (R

chart), which monitors population variance (σ^2) using the range (R = maximum – minimum) of each sample.

2.1. NORMAL DISTRIBUTION

Normal distribution is one of the most important distributions in statistics and quality control. Visually, this distribution is bell-shaped, symmetrical, and the function value tends to zero as the variable approaches negative or positive infinity. The probability density function is given by equation 1. The meaning of this distribution is represented by μ and the standard deviation by σ . Figure 1 describes its shape.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2}, \quad \text{to } -\infty < x < \infty \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 – Normal Distribution Curve.

Source: Author's own elaboration (2025)

Every normal distribution, when adding and subtracting one standard deviation from the mean, contains approximately 68% of the values, approximately 95% when adding and subtracting two standard deviations from the mean, and 99.7% when adding and subtracting three standard deviations from the mean. Figure 1 illustrates this characteristic.

2.2. SAMPLING DISTRIBUTION OF THE MEAN AND CENTRAL LIMIT THEOREM

Sample-based decision making is known as statistical inference, and much of this procedure is based on knowledge of the distribution of the characteristics of the statistic used in the sample, called the sampling distribution. If the statistic used in the investigation is the sample mean (\bar{x}), this distribution is known as the sampling distribution of the mean, and the central limit theorem describes the characteristics of this distribution.

“For a simple random sample (X_1, \dots, X_n), drawn from a population with mean μ and finite variance σ^2 , the sampling distribution of the mean (\bar{x}) approximates, for large n , a normal distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2/n .” (BUSSAB; MORETTIN, 2010).

2.3. HYPOTHESIS TESTING

According to MONTGOMERY (2009), hypothesis testing involves making statements about the values of the parameters of a probability distribution, and the conclusions are based on sample data and are subject to error. The errors that can occur are called Type I Error and Type II Error.

In the hypothesis testing setup, it is necessary to define two hypotheses: the null hypothesis (H_0), which is an initial statement about the parameter's value, and the alternative hypothesis, which contradicts the null hypothesis.

The conclusion of a hypothesis test depends on the statistic used and the probability distribution of the sample. If the statistic used is the sample mean, the test's conclusion is based on the normal distribution, assuming σ^2 is known. Depending on the values obtained from the sample, the decision in a hypothesis test is to either reject or not reject the null hypothesis, based on the probability of committing a previously established error, called the significance level.

2.3.1. TYPES OF ERRORS

Rejecting the null hypothesis implies that the alternative hypothesis holds for the population parameter, but since the values for this statement come from a random sample, it may be false and is thus called a Type I error. The probability of a Type I error is called the significance level, and Equation 2 defines it.

$$\alpha = P\{\text{type I error}\} = P\{\text{reject } H_0 | H_0 \text{ is true}\} \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, not rejecting the null hypothesis implies indicating that there is no statistical evidence that the alternative hypothesis is true, but, since the values for this come from a random sample, this claim may be false and thus called a Type II Error, and the probability of a Type II error is described in equation 3.

$$\beta = P\{\text{type II error}\} = P\{\text{stop rejecting } H_0 | H_0 \text{ is false}\} \quad (3)$$

2.4. CONTROL CHART

A control chart is basically composed of three horizontal lines called the Upper Control Limit (UCL), Lower Control Limit (LCL), and Center Line (CL), and several interconnected and equally spaced points that are derived from the statistics of each sample collected over time. Figure 2 shows a typical control chart.

When the process is operating under normal conditions, the variation in the points is due solely to inherent process causes. In this condition, the process is considered under control, and the points follow a normal distribution.

However, if any malfunction occurs during the process, the points tend to exhibit greater variation, resulting in more product defects. In this condition, the process is said to be out of control, and the points tend to exhibit different patterns that distinguish it from a process under control.

From a statistical-methods perspective, the point patterns correspond to hypothesis testing, where the null hypothesis assumes the process is under control, and the alternative hypothesis assumes it is out of control. If the points form an out-of-control pattern (alarm), the production process should be

evaluated for repair.

Figure 2 – Control Chart.

Source: Author's own elaboration (2025).

One problem in the design of control charts is the occurrence of false alarms, and the number of false alarms is a factor to be considered. The average number of inspections until a false alarm occurs (ARL – Average Run Length) is defined by equation 4; the higher the ARL, the fewer unnecessary stops should occur in the process.

$$ARL = \frac{1}{P(\text{false alarm} \mid \text{process under control})} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \quad (4)$$

2.4.1. MEAN CHART (CHART \bar{x})

The mean control chart monitors the meaning of a process (μ) that is under control. The points on the chart are the mean (\bar{x}) derived from sample data of size “n” at each point in time. The limits of the mean charts are described in equations 5 to 7.

$$LIC_{\bar{x}} = \mu + k \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (5)$$

$$LIC_{\bar{x}} = \mu \quad (6)$$

$$LIC_{\bar{x}} = \mu - k \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (7)$$

Where “k” corresponds to the number of standard deviations away from the mean, and if $k = 1$, approximately 68% of the points are contained within this interval, if $k = 2$, approximately 95% of the points are contained within this interval, and if $k = 3$, approximately 99.7% of the points are contained within this interval. These percentages are known because the distribution of means is normal. Traditional charts use $k = 3$.

In charts with $k = 3$, it is possible to separate the range above and below the center line into 3 equally spaced bands, each band corresponding to the width of one standard deviation. In Figure 3, these are labeled F1, F2, and F3. The bands are used to identify some of the out-of-control process patterns. The band associated with F3 is called the warning band because it is close to the control limits.

2.5. POINT PATTERNS ON A MEAN CONTROL CHART

The process is said to be in control when the points follow a normal distribution, and each new point does not generate any out-of-control patterns. Shewhart defined the out-of-control pattern as the occurrence of a point outside the control limits, as shown in Figure 3.

Source: Author's own elaboration (2025)

The probability of a false alarm for this pattern is 0.0026998, and the average response time (ARL) is approximately 370 inspections before a false alarm occurs.

Juran's text (1982) suggests that the process may be out of control if it follows one of the ten-point patterns described in Table 1. Control chart developers can choose patterns for process monitoring, and it is common to use the first pattern in the table and supplement it with the others. One problem with using multiple patterns is the increased likelihood of false alarms, which is the subject of this work.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This work is theoretical in nature and uses Monte Carlo simulation (Fishman, 1996) to estimate the number of false alarms based on the out-of-control pattern described in Table 1. The alarm types studied were the five described as: AF_1, AF_2, AF_3, AF_4, and AF_5.

The first type of alarm, created by Shewhart, will be used in all simulations, as the others are considered complementary. The programming language used to obtain the results is Python. The code is available on GitHub at https://github.com/jcgsoares/Analise_Alarmes_Falsos.git.

Table 1. Pattern of out-of-control points.

Description	Description of the out-of-control dot pattern
AF_1.	A point outside the control limits.
AF_2.	Two out of three consecutive points between the warning zone, but all within the control limits.
AF_3.	Four or five consecutive points in the same area of the center line and beyond the limits of one sigma.
AF_4.	Six consecutive points upward or downward and within the control limits.
AF_5.	A sequence of eight consecutive points on the same side of the center line, all within the control limits.
AF_6.	Fourteen points in sequence, alternating between up and down.
AF_7.	Fifteen consecutive points within the one-sigma range.
AF_8.	Eight consecutive points with no points in the warning zone.
AF_9.	An unusual or non-random pattern in the data.
AF_10.	One or more points near an alert or control threshold.

Fonte: Elaboração própria.

3.1. ALGORITHM AND FLOWCHART

The Flowchart in Figure 4 shows how the program used in the simulation works. The process begins by defining the fundamental parameters for constructing the control chart: the mean, the standard deviation, and the sample size.

Figure 4 – Flowchart of the Simulator Algorithm.

Source: Author's own elaboration.

Next, the system generates samples and calculates their respective averages. For each new average, the algorithm checks whether it triggers any alarm, starting with the function corresponding to Alarm 1. If this is not triggered, the process

continues testing the other functions, up to Alarm “n”. When an alarm is triggered, the number of inspections performed up to that point is stored. If no alarm is triggered, a new sample is generated, and the cycle repeats.

This process continues until the predefined number of cycles is reached. At the end, the algorithm calculates the average number of inspections, determines the average execution time for each type of alarm, and finally presents the results.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In all simulations, the number of repetitions was 50,000 times, and the reference value for a false alarm is the alarm of a point outside the control limits (AF_1). Table 2 shows the false alarm ARL values for each alarm type.

Quadro 2. ARL de alarme falso.

Types of alarms	ARL
AF_1	370,40
AF_2	302,04
AF_3	300,89
AF_4	412,75
AF_5	256,59

Source: Author's own elaboration.

Alarm AF_4 has the highest ARL, indicating that the probability of this alarm is lower than AF_1, while AF_5 has the highest probability of occurrence. Table 3 describes the percentage of occurrence of each alarm type in combinations and the ARL value.

When combining alarm types with AF_1, a decrease in false-alarm ARL is observed, as expected. Combining two alarms can reduce the number of false alarms by approximately 50%, three by approximately 65%, four by approximately 75%, and five by approximately 80%.

Alarm type AF_5, when combined with others, occurs most frequently, and adding it as an out-of-control indication tends to increase the number of false alarms in the monitoring. Alarm type AF_4 has the least impact on the frequency of false alarms.

Table 3. Percentages of false alarms and ARLs.

% de ocorrência em 50.000 simulações					ARL
AF_1	-----	-----	-----	-----	370,4
100,0%					
AF_1	AF_2	-----	-----	-----	166,2
44,7%	55,3%				
AF_1	AF_3	-----	-----	-----	164,3
45,1%	54,9%				
AF_1	AF_4	-----	-----	-----	196,7
53,9%	46,1%				
AF_1	AF_5	-----	-----	-----	150,2
40,9%	59,1%				
AF_1	AF_2	AF_3	-----	-----	109,0
30,2%	36,2%	33,6%			
AF_1	AF_2	AF_4	-----	-----	120,5
32,8%	39,3%	27,8%			
AF_1	AF_2	AF_5	-----	-----	101,3
27,9%	33,8%	38,3%			
AF_1	AF_3	AF_4	-----	-----	120,6
32,7%	40,2%	27,1%			
AF_1	AF_3	AF_5	-----	-----	105,1
28,2%	34,4%	37,4%			
AF_1	AF_4	AF_5	-----	-----	114,4
31,1%	25,6%	43,3%			
AF_1	AF_2	AF_3	AF_4	-----	89,1
24,2%	29,0%	27,0%	19,8%		
AF_1	AF_2	AF_3	AF_5	-----	79,8
21,6%	26,2%	24,1%	28,1%		
AF_1	AF_3	AF_4	AF_5	-----	86,9
23,4%	28,2%	19,0%	29,4%		
AF_1	AF_2	AF_3	AF_4	AF_5	68,4
18,7%	22,8%	20,6%	14,6%	23,4%	

Fonte: Elaboração Própria.

5. CONCLUSION

In designing control charts, managers evaluate the charts' sensitivity to process mismatches. In this case, the faster the problem is detected, the lower the quality cost; however, it also tends to increase the number of false alarms, which increases the cost.

This paper quantifies the average number of false alarms on the average control chart, depending on the type of out-of-control point pattern used. Table 3, developed in this paper, allows managers to predict the percentage of false alarms that may occur when using two or more out-of-control point patterns.

The frequency of false alarms increases with the number of false alarm patterns and can double when using two of them; when using five, it can reduce the ARL

by up to 80% compared to the Shewhart alarm initially triggered by a point outside the control limits.

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